

Assessing Resilience Impacts from Integrated Above- and Below-ground Urban Infrastructure

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses an appropriate framework and metrics for infrastructure analysis that can include complex systems representations for all sectors – physical, social and environmental. In order to make better decisions concerning the use of underground space, particularly in urban environments, the functions and operations of the human and physical infrastructure systems must be understood in an integrated framework with common and meaningful metrics and representations. Considering the importance of economics, sustainability and vulnerability to extreme events, decision makers need an understanding of the valuation for underground space as a resource in order to consider life-cycle engineering and trade-offs and pros and cons of above- and below-ground infrastructure investments.

INTRODUCTION

Physical infrastructure systems provide water, sewer, transportation, energy, and communications – the critical services that are the essence of our increasingly urban society. These distribution and transmission systems deliver the services we rely on and expect – they contribute public good, even though they are often managed by private entities. Since being initially designed and installed as simple, linear and uncoupled systems, they have been added to, repaired, and connected in new ways so that the decomposable systems of the past have become the tightly coupled, nonlinear and intractable complex systems of the present. They develop emergent behaviors that defy control in an absolute sense, particularly when these systems are asked to perform under conditions of crisis and disasters.

Our national infrastructure may be valued at between \$50 and \$80 Trillion, perhaps more. This is equivalent to \$200k to \$300k for each U.S. citizen as his/her birthright, and this suggests that we are warranted to consider that the nation's infrastructure is a pre-investment upon which the economic engine runs, the quality of life is assured, and career developments of each individual are leveraged.

However, the US public and private infrastructure is aging. State-of-practice design and operation from the past has led to robust-enough systems for which we have sufficient experience to permit simplifying assumptions that enabled operation with minimal monitoring. There were sufficient reserves for acceptable service under known stress. But as we interconnect aging systems into larger networks, and observe decreasing performance levels, reductions in excess capacity and new stresses (e.g., poorly understood interdependencies, attack), we learn that our systems have lost robustness. As our system complexity has increased, many of the design simplifications are no longer acceptable, and new concepts of design and control provide an opportunity for new approaches to system management.

Sustainable urban underground development must meet current human needs while conserving spatial resources and the natural and built environments for future generations to meet their needs. This requires a systems perspective for integrated above and below ground resource use

and management, and must include consideration of cost effectiveness, longevity, functionality, safety, aesthetics and quality of life, upgradeability and adaptability, and minimization of negative impacts while maximizing environmental benefits, resilience, and reliability (Bobylev 2009).

Over the past century, we have experienced dramatic changes in demographics, and we can look forward to a world in which existing sociotechnical systems will be operated with increasing sophistication of control through dedicated information and communications technology (ICT) links, making them effectively cyberphysical systems. The interconnection of aging physical infrastructure systems into larger networks, and the loss of redundancy associated with high efficiency operations has led to reduced reliability and poorly understood interdependencies. To complicate matters, our cyberphysical infrastructure has not been maintained, causing unexpected vulnerabilities and cascading failures (ASCE, 2017; AWWA, 2001). To reduce the vulnerability and increase our understanding requires a commitment to research that can only be accomplished through a multi-disciplinary approach focused on the normal, day-to-day operations as well as the response of these systems to the impact of extreme events of natural, technological, or human-initiated origin. The problem is multi-faceted and is embodied within the expertise of such disciplines as engineering, mathematics, natural sciences, information and computer science, decision and risk management, economics and other social and behavioral sciences.

As extreme events frequency and the magnitude of resulting disasters have increased, unexpected performance response, and lack of resilience have been noted (Sanford Bernhardt and McNeil, 2008). While there has been success in modelling complex response and predicting behaviors of our urban sociotechnical networks under stress, the models have grown so complex that data is not available to validate the model predictions (NRC, 2009).

However, as a nation and a world, we will become increasingly urban, with competition for surface space becoming ever more intense. The underground must add to the desirability and vitality of the urban experience – and our underground designs must uplift and inspire those who use and visit the urban environment. Therefore, it is important to make underground infrastructure systems reliable and resilient. We also need to understand why the public may view underground space as undesirable, so we need to understand:

- How is underground space planning best integrated with surface space planning, which depends on the subsurface geology, geographic constraints, past usage, society and culture?
- How can we effectively assess life-cycle performance, which requires that we are able to attach a value to underground space as a resource (separate from mineral rights and material resource development)?
- How can we model the performance of our complex systems, combinations of old and new with increasing interdependencies, under normal and stressed operations?
- Can we understand how natural and technological hazards evolve into disasters, and how to make our communities and above and below-ground infrastructure systems more resilient to extreme events?

It is clear that we need to understand our sociotechnical system dynamics and resilience at a fundamental level or we will learn the wrong lessons from the past. Resilience is a significant concept to many fields including psychology, economics, ecology, or even governance systems. According to the Resilience Alliance (<http://www.resalliance.org/576.php>) and as applied to ecosystems, metrics for resilience have three defining characteristics: the amount of change the

system can undergo and still retain the same controls on function and structure; the degree to which the system is capable of self-organization; and the ability to build and increase the capacity for learning and adaptation.

Here, resilience is defined as the ability (sufficient capacity and/or flexibility) of a system to experience unexpected shocks or perturbations, and to respond and recover functionality at some acceptable level of performance or action. We have an urgent need for improved understanding of the genesis and evolution of resilience, in particular in urban and coastal regions. We need to build and enhance social and ecological capital and community resilience, as well as to increase system adaptive capacity (including self-organization) and improve the cost-effectiveness of investments in sociotechnical (human, cyber and physical) infrastructure systems.

RESILIENCE FRAMEWORK

The focus for resiliency is on functionality and ability to adapt and restore functionality, including planned and spontaneous responses. To understand the evolution of a resilient response in an urban environment, an interdisciplinary approach is needed that captures attributes of the complex environmental, human and physical systems in a region. In addition, the concept of what is an appropriate responding region itself needs to be investigated through development of layered and registered data resources. These models require the assembly of varied and deep information reflecting current and future conditions, response and usage so that we can expand our knowledge and validate our discoveries and predictions for system performance response. With these assembled information and modelling resources, we can develop a framework of variables and relationships that will support a cross-disciplinary exploration of resilience on a common, integrated, cross-sector basis, and build knowledge as we develop and test theory and models about the resilience of complex socio-technical systems. Only then can we answer important questions including:

- What observations (evidence) can we make (identify) to indicate qualitatively whether a specific system or network will demonstrate resiliency?
- What metrics can be used to evaluate the capacity of a system or network for resilient response?
- How does resiliency develop or evolve in response, and what factors control or influence the development? Is it a process with thresholds, tipping points, state changes, or is it a continuous function?
- What can we understand about when investment or adaptive management is warranted to improve resiliency of a system of systems, networks, and interdependent systems?

A number of sector-specific models (e.g., telecommunications, electric power) of system performance are currently available (Lee et al., 2007) that are more comprehensive in terms of both their geographical scope and the level of detail they capture, and more sophisticated in terms of how effectively they represent, to operational personnel, the information they can produce. But not all sectors have been addressed, and the models are relatively primitive (e.g. employing disparate, ad-hoc implementations, and not interoperable across geographical service areas) for other sectors. A close analogy between physical infrastructure systems (the focus here) and social systems (e.g., disease) and virtual systems (e.g., Internet) is notable, as is the observation that many of the solution methods in complex systems science are common to all applications. Lacking is a consistent methodology for modelling cross- sector behaviors of critical infrastructures under stress.

As a foundation for integrated study of complex system resilience, it will be important to develop Performance Response Functions (PRFs) that serve as the backbone curves for system response. Performance response concepts have been introduced before (e.g., Bruneau et al., 2003; Silverman, 2004; Fwa, 2005; Rose, 2009; Reed et al., 2010), but PRFs have a greater potential for breakthrough insights in evaluating what performance means, establishing cross-sector performance metrics and variables (the resilience framework), and understanding how system performance response functions (PRFs) record or reflect important aspects of system behavior at different temporal and spatial scales.

As an example, consider Figure 1, which shows PRFs for socio-technical system performance. The green area represents the loss in performance of system A with respect to a specific event (e.g., storm, earthquake, terrorist act), measured as quality degradation from pre-event “normal” performance over time. The vertical scale is some metric for system performance, which could be based on service delivered, an econometric measure, etc. The response depends on system capacity relative to event magnitude and scale, how well the system has been maintained, how intense the event is, the pre-preparation of the community for such an event, and the geography and social structure of the community and region. In the case of system A, the impact was minimized in intensity and duration, and recovery was rapid reflective of a high level of resilience. In the case of system C, the system failed and recovery was not possible.

It is important that resilience be appreciated and characterized as a system response representing the return to service or functionality, and the restoration of trust and well-being. As such, we need fundamental investigations into PRF metrics that include contributions from the social environment (human/organizational capital and capacity), the physical environment (infrastructural systems), and the natural environment (eco-systems). Any measurement of resilience will depend on the definition of the region being considered to include spatial and temporal scales, boundaries, and the model level of detail or granularity.

Figure 1. Conceptual Definition of Performance Response Functions A- highly resilient system, B – less resilient system (may not fully recover) C – loss of resiliency – system failure (after Nelson and Sterling, 2012)

Conceptually, resilience is a very useful concept but the data required for its application is not often obtained, and the assessment of integrated urban resilience is not yet widely recognized nor utilized by practitioners. Neither has the linkage between currently defined outcomes/metrics been made with standards or policy incentives an important aspect of implementation.

PRF ANALYSIS AS A METAMODEL RESILIENCE FRAMEWORK

PRFs can also be viewed as a kind of metamodel outcome that reflects the functionality of the system(s) but without the sensitivity toward privacy and security that exists for some descriptive data sets. Convolution of performance response functions for different but interdependent above- and below-ground systems informs the development of a new science of resiliency that can effectively be applied across sectors and systems. This work involves establishing metrics for characterizing infrastructure robustness and fragility, but the metrics must also be applicable to sociotechnical organizations to begin to capture and model community resilience as an integrative and vital concept for our increasingly urban world. This work will lead to enhanced interpretations of the behavior of interdependent infrastructures, thus contributing to systems theory of integrated sociotechnical system behavior, particularly under conditions of increasing density and underground development. In this way, the importance of investment in the urban underground can be demonstrated as a key element of sustainable and life-cycle approaches to better planning and construction in our urban environments.

While we can construct PRFs for specific components of the infrastructure (Croope and McNeil 2011) and we can observe PRFs for regions or communities using data censored by time (Hallegatte 2008), constructing PRF's to assist decision makers and allocate resources requires us to understand scale, aggregation, interactions and interdependencies. PRFs can also serve as a framework to consider use of new technologies, evaluate strategic investments, or introduce stresses to systems. PRF concepts may be applied to individual systems, or all systems in a region. With coupled models, PRFs can be used to explore how the performance/behavior changes as a function of degree and type of interconnectivity of systems in a sector and across sectors, and across temporal and spatial scales.

Models and metrics for resilience have been the subject of much recent work (Gilbert, 2010), and examples of metrics for resiliency and/or PRFs include:

- Services – infrastructure function delivery (e.g., pressure, volume, rate, quality, reliability).
- Human activity (e.g., trips taken, tickets bought, calls made, population density, other demographics).
- Economics (e.g., income statistics, sales tax paid, targeted purchases).

Given a record of spatially distributed pertinent information over many time intervals, the geography and variation of a metric may yield understanding about how the region responds, where resources come from that aid in recovery – ultimately laying the bases for a prediction of comparative resiliency among different communities and societies. When integrated over space and time, the resulting character of the PRFs may indicate typical shape functions. If so, then a new science of complex system analysis of PRFs and resilience may be explored in which a fundamental understanding of how metric functions vary as a function of spatial, temporal and intensity effects and regional boundaries (and perhaps characteristics of boundaries) can be achieved. This would include building an understanding about how PRFs differ (or are the

same) across scales, sectors, and systems. The prospect of a science of resilience and PRFs may actually have its own algebra for representing multi- system performance responses.

Demands for infrastructure service vary over time but have typically been assumed constant (Tierney and Trainor, 2004). This assumption must be carefully examined, e.g., the supply side of transportation systems can be measured by metrics such as accessibility, travel time and capacity using risk assessment methods, but the supply-demand relationship has not been captured. PRFs can be used to explore individual system vulnerability, develop summary indicators of net resilience of all systems providing satisfaction to this demand, and to assess topological properties of a networked infrastructure as well as interactions between network structures when subjected to disturbance. These properties include the shortest path distance, clustering coefficients, network density, vertex degree, node and link “betweenness” centralities, network connectivity loss and efficiency.

By keeping track of the history of the system through a memory kernel as dictated by data and event modelling, it is possible to develop new quantitative performance models of infrastructure systems (Lee et al., 2007). However, the challenge is to define more specific measures which will integrate across resilience computations in economics or social sciences.

INTERDEPENDENCIES AND RESILIENCE

The major elements of sustainability are increasingly a fundamental requirement to the successful undertaking of large capital construction programs – effectively constituting a social license for a “balanced solution.” We need to create a methodology and the resources that will establish the value of subsurface space as a resource in urban environments – one that enhances sustainability and urban system resiliency (for example, see Allouche et al., 2008 for the impact of Hurricane Katrina on buried utility services]. Our sociotechnical systems are interdependent, so that disruption of one infrastructure system can impact the operation of other systems. Sources of interdependencies are varied and include technological, cyber, geographic and spatial, economics and business, social/human, political/policy/legal, organizational, resources and supply chains, and security.

Figure 2 illustrates interdependencies that may be developed among six physical infrastructure sectors, and illustrates the complexity of performance and behavior of these systems. In some cases, geospatial mining tools for data-rich sectors have been used to explore the interdependencies, e.g., among transportation and energy systems by merging geospatial and nonspatial data (Shih et al., 2009). Such compound system resiliency analysis will likely lead to new understandings of compound system performance and sources of vulnerabilities.

The resilience of our urban communities depends on many factors that extend beyond the physical system complexities and interdependencies. Therefore, social network research is needed to provide linked and registered metrics for event impacts, yielding change trajectories over time (Anex, et al., 2006, Bobylev, 2009, 2016). Social networks in use now represent a new resource that allows researchers access to social data quickly, and software designed to analyze word function and content on social media (such as blogs) and on-line information sources can be used to capture and analyze the public's acute reactions to extreme events (Sherrieb et al., 2010), providing an exciting window into social resilience.

Figure 2. Interdependencies for Six Sectors of Infrastructure (Rinaldi et al., 2001)

CONCLUSIONS

Are human creations durable enough to stand up to time? Can we measure their strength and adaptive capability? What is the value of underground space and how can it be best used to improve urban infrastructure service and resilience. It is important to tackle these as principal questions that has perplexed scholars in the natural, social, and engineering sciences as well as the humanities—what are the elements of survival of social and built systems? Such questions have engaged scholars since antiquity, and emerge in both classical descriptions and more modern studies of the growth trajectory, and decline of great civilizations.

The complexities of technical and architectural development on an increasingly urbanized planet is elevated in importance as people and resources are increasingly concentrated. Critics such as Perrow (2007) argue that these characteristics of modernity are just the advance guard of more and greater catastrophes. Recent cataclysms support his views: the collapse of the Twin Towers of the World Trade Center fatally damaged even very large buildings in their environs, while more recently, the Japan Tohoku earthquake and tsunami wrecked habitation, industry, and commerce on a broad scale and forced unprecedented multiple simultaneous nuclear emergencies. These events emerged as surprises that, though envisioned (Mitchell, 1996), surpassed the scale of extant planning and demanded solutions that were as expedient as they

were inventive. The burgeoning growth of resilience studies offers an advanced and scientifically valid approach to understanding capacities for system survival. Wildavsky (1988) suggested that in a dilemma between anticipation and resilience, resilience was to be preferred in most cases because many threats cannot be anticipated. Others (e.g., Kendra and Wachtendorf, 2007) argued that the distinction between anticipation and resilience is not so absolute, because resilience owes much to anticipating needs as well as to creativity and improvisation. What to plan for, how durable our creations need to be, what we must look forward to, and how we can improvise in crisis comprise the basic knowledge of resilience—survival—that we will study as we build a science of resilience – one that includes both above- and below-ground resources as an integrated environment for the urban quality of life.

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